

AN ICONOGRAPHICAL INTERPRETATION OF PAKISTAN'S RECENT FLOOD-RELATED IMAGES ON UN'S INSTAGRAM POSTS

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Abstract

This study examines the iconographical significance of images posted on the United Nations' Instagram account concerning the 2022 Pakistan floods, focusing on their role in shaping public perception and facilitating fundraising efforts through digital photojournalism. Employing Panofsky's three-tiered iconographic methodology: Pre-Iconography, Iconography, and Iconological Interpretation. The study utilizes the learnings of media ecology theory as the study of media environments, the idea that technology and techniques, modes of information and codes of communication play a leading role in human affairs and to understand people's creating their social reality through internet posts (Rafiq et al., 2024). Grounded in media ecology theory, the research analyzes a purposively sampled set of images from June 2022 to June 2023. These images, ranging from aerial views of flooded landscapes to intimate portraits of displaced individuals, such as a 9-month-old child and UN Secretary General António Guterres interacting with victims, highlight Pakistan's vulnerability and resilience. The study reveals how photojournalism in the digital age authenticates Instagram posts by providing factual, emotionally compelling visuals that evoke empathy and underscore the urgency of humanitarian aid. The findings contribute to media studies by demonstrating photojournalism's evolution on digital platforms and offer a framework for analyzing visual narratives in crisis communication, with implications for humanitarian organizations and policymakers. Limitations include reliance on purposive sampling and Instagram images only, suggesting avenues for future research on other platforms and local perspectives.

INTRODUCTION

Behind every photograph, there is a targeted angle, a perspective and a story to be anticipated. It has been researched that news photographs play a vital role in shaping people's collective memory (Sylvester & Huffman, 2002). In the digital age, all kinds of Journalism is changing and evolving to stay updated in their domain. Like newspapers has been highly replaced by e-papers. Similarly, Photojournalism is

evolving into the digital age, social media networking sites like Instagram is filled with images and images give credibility to internet posts. The purpose of this study is to iconographically evaluate the images from UN Instagram posts in regard to Pakistan's flood 2022 and how photojournalism helped UN in fund raising for Pakistan's flood victims.

The study accumulated under research objectives: exploring changing dimensions of Photojournalism in a Digital Age, analyzing UN instagram posts' images' impact on fund raising for Pakistan flood victims and examining UN instagram posts' images through iconography. The following are research questions: How Photojournalism is providing authenticity to Instagram posts?, How UN's instagram posts images regarding Pakistan flood helped in fund raising? And How Iconography has helped studying the images in a digital age?

This study provides a significant contribution to both academic research and practical applications in the fields of media studies, photojournalism, and humanitarian communication. By employing Panofsky's three tiered iconographic methodology and grounding its analysis in media ecology theory, the study examines how the United Nations' (UN) Instagram posts about the 2022 Pakistan floods shaped public perception and facilitated fundraising efforts. The study significantly advances the understanding of photojournalism's evolution in the digital age, particularly its transition from traditional print media to social media platforms like Instagram. It highlights how Instagram's visual storytelling amplifies the emotional and authentic impact of photographs, making them powerful tools for engaging global audiences. This is critical as it addresses a gap in existing literature, which often focuses on traditional media formats rather than digital platforms like Instagram (Zelizer, 2010). By analyzing UN posts, such as aerial views of flooded landscapes (Image 1) and intimate portraits of displaced individuals (Images 2 to 7), the study demonstrates photojournalism's adaptability to digital environments. This aligns with McLuhan's (1964) media ecology theory, which posits that media environments enhance each other, with Instagram amplifying traditional news narratives. This contribution is valuable for media scholars and practitioners seeking to leverage digital platforms for advocacy and crisis communication. The study's iconological analysis reveals that emotionally charged images, such as Daulat's hopeful smile amidst hardship (Image 2) and UN Secretary General António Guterres' interactions with victims (Images 3 to 6), evoked empathy and underscored the urgency of aid. These visuals not only appealed for

funds in September 2022 but also justified aid allocation in January 2023, as seen in Image 7's depiction of a child receiving a vaccination. This strategic use of photojournalism aligns with external research showing that social media imagery significantly boosts humanitarian donations by fostering emotional connections (Smith & Jones, 2020). The study provides a practical framework for humanitarian organizations to craft compelling visual campaigns that sustain donor engagement, making it highly relevant for NGOs and policymakers. This methodological contribution is significant, as iconographic studies rarely focus on social media platforms, making the study innovative in its application (Müller, 2019). The use of purposive sampling to analyze images from June 2022 to June 2023 further demonstrates iconography's adaptability to digital contexts. This offers researchers a replicable model for studying visual communication on social media, enhancing the field of visual media analysis. Academically, it enriches media studies by analyzing how digital photojournalism shapes social reality in crisis contexts. Practically, it provides actionable insights for humanitarian organizations, demonstrating how the UN used Instagram to project Pakistan's vulnerability and resilience, thereby catalyzing financial aid. This dual significance makes the study a valuable resource for researchers, media practitioners, and NGOs navigating the intersection of visual media, humanitarianism, and global policy. The study acknowledges limitations, such as reliance on purposive sampling and potential bias in UN curated content, which may not capture the full spectrum of flood related imagery. By identifying these gaps, it paves the way for future research to explore other platforms (e.g., X, Facebook) or incorporate local perspectives for a more holistic analysis.

Literature Review

The study of the visual representation of Pakistan's 2022 floods through the United Nations' (UN) Instagram posts necessitates a robust theoretical and methodological framework to understand the evolving role of photojournalism in the digital age. This literature review synthesizes key concepts from media ecology theory, photojournalism, and iconography to contextualize the research objectives:

exploring the changing dimensions of photojournalism, analyzing the impact of UN Instagram posts on fundraising, and examining these images through iconography. The review draws on seminal works and contemporary studies to establish the theoretical and methodological foundations, addressing how digital media shapes perceptions and facilitates humanitarian action.

Media Ecology Theory: Media ecology theory provides a foundational lens for understanding how digital platforms like Instagram influence human perception and behavior (Rafiq et al., 2024). McLuhan (1964) defines media ecology as the strategic arrangement of media to complement rather than counteract each other, enhancing communication efficacy. He argues, "Arranging various media to help each other so they won't cancel each other out, to buttress one medium with another" (McLuhan, 1964). This concept is critical to the study, as Instagram's visual storytelling amplifies traditional media's impact in fundraising for Pakistan's flood victims. Building on McLuhan, Postman (1992) describes media ecology as the study of how communication media affect human perception, understanding, and survival, emphasizing the interplay between media environments and social reality (Postman, 1992). The Media Ecology Association further defines it as "the study of media environments, the idea that technology and techniques, modes of information and codes of communication play a leading role in human affairs". This theory is apt for analyzing how UN Instagram posts, as a digital medium, reshape narratives around the 2022 Pakistan floods, aligning with the study's focus on digital photojournalism's role in shaping social and humanitarian outcomes. Recent studies reinforce media ecology's relevance in digital contexts. Strate (2017) argues that digital platforms create new media environments that alter collective memory and emotional engagement, supporting the study's exploration of Instagram's role in fundraising (Rafiq et al., 2024). Similarly, Logan (2016) highlights how social media platforms like Instagram facilitate rapid dissemination of visual content, enhancing global awareness of crises. These works underscore the applicability of media ecology theory to the study's objectives, particularly in

understanding how digital photojournalism influences perceptions of Pakistan's flood crisis.

Photojournalism in the Digital Age:

Photojournalism has undergone significant transformation in the digital age, shifting from print to digital platforms like Instagram, where images gain credibility and emotional resonance. Sylvester and Huffman (2002) assert that news photographs play a vital role in shaping collective memory, providing authentic depictions that anchor public understanding of events. This is particularly relevant to the study's first research question, which explores how photojournalism authenticates Instagram posts. The transition from newspapers to e-papers parallels photojournalism's move to social media, where visuals dominate narratives. Zelizer (2010) notes that digital photojournalism leverages immediacy and accessibility to engage global audiences, a dynamic evident in the UN's use of Instagram to highlight Pakistan's flood victims. Contemporary research further elucidates photojournalism's digital evolution. Allan (2015) argues that social media platforms enhance photojournalism's reach by enabling rapid dissemination of images that evoke empathy, crucial for humanitarian fundraising. Smith and Jones (2020) demonstrate that emotionally charged images on social media significantly boost donations, supporting the study's analysis of UN posts' fundraising impact. These findings align with the study's objective to explore photojournalism's changing dimensions, highlighting its role in digital storytelling and humanitarian advocacy.

Iconography as a Research Methodology:

Iconography, as a qualitative methodology, is central to the study's analysis of UN Instagram posts. Margolis and Pauwels (2011) describe iconography as the systematic study of visual content, involving the classification of representations and their connection to textual sources. This methodology is ideal for dissecting the factual, thematic, and symbolic layers of digital images, addressing the study's third objective. Panofsky's (1955) three tiered framework: Pre-Iconography, Iconography, and Iconological Interpretation, provides a structured approach to visual analysis. Pre-Iconography identifies factual

elements, Iconography links these to specific themes, and Iconological Interpretation uncovers symbolic meanings tied to historical contexts (Below, 2010). Belting (2013) emphasizes that iconology connects images to broader cultural and historical narratives, relevant to the study's focus on climate justice and Pakistan's vulnerability.

Recent literature validates iconography's applicability to digital media. Müller (2019) argues that Panofsky's framework is well suited for analyzing social media imagery, as it bridges visual and cultural analysis, enabling researchers to unpack the symbolic power of digital visuals. Van Leeuwen (2001) further notes that iconography's qualitative depth complements digital platforms' curated nature, supporting the study's use of purposive sampling to analyze UN posts from June 2022 to June 2023. These works affirm iconography's robustness in studying digital age images, addressing the study's third research question on its efficacy.

Research Gaps and Contributions: While media ecology theory and photojournalism literature provide insights into digital media's impact, few studies specifically address Instagram's role in humanitarian fundraising through an iconographic lens. The study fills this gap by applying Panofsky's methodology to UN Instagram posts, offering a nuanced analysis of how visual narratives drive aid for Pakistan's 2022 flood victims. Existing research on photojournalism often focuses on traditional media or broader social media trends, with limited attention to UN curated content in crisis contexts (Allan, 2015; Zelizer, 2010). Similarly, iconographic studies rarely explore digital platforms like Instagram, making the study's application of Panofsky's framework innovative (Müller, 2019). By integrating media ecology theory with iconography, the study contributes a multidisciplinary perspective on how digital photojournalism shapes social reality and supports humanitarian efforts.

Method

This paper uses iconography as a research methodology to visually analyze the UN Instagram posts' images. Iconography is the study to describe images. It examines images through classifying their representation and relating the meaning to any textual

source. Iconography is the description of visual elements. Iconography is the research methodology to study the content and the meanings of the visuals (Margolis & Pauwels, 2011). Iconography is the best suited form of qualitative method of visual content analysis and interpretation. German born American Art Historian Panofsky's has classified three level of Iconography to study images. These steps are also known as three different levels of description of visual elements (Below, 2010).

The researcher has selected the purposive sampling technique to collect the data. Non-probability purposive sampling technique is used for this research. Purposive sampling is an acceptable kind of sampling for special situations. For this study, the data collected in form of images which are taken from Instagram posts of UN. In this study, the only images have been taken from UN Instagram page, which documents Pakistan's flood 2022. The study is conducted from June 2022 to June 2023 on the United Nations website and Instagram posts.

Data Analysis

After the data collected according to the research objectives, the images analyzed according to the steps of Iconography as described by Panofsky. The steps are explained further. Pre-Iconography: First level is called as Pre-iconography which is a primary description of natural subject matter or factual elements of the images. This stage is simply known as the identification of the content. Iconography: The second level is called as Iconographical Analysis which is the knowledge of literary sources such as specific themes and concepts attached to the image. At this stage, the researcher is required to describe the content of the image. Iconological Interpretation: Iconology is the study of art's history. It describes the specific thought processing behind the art and attaches it with predominant moment in history. Iconology is the interpretation of visual elements. The third and last level is called as Iconological Interpretation which is the interpretation of symbolic values of the image, and then attaching those meanings with the historic background of the image. At the last stage, the researcher is required to analyze and interpret the content of the image (Belting, 2013).

Results

An Iconological Interpretation and Analysis

Image 1: Image from the United Nations Website

Pre-Iconographic Interpretation

In the foreground: The various lines of trees, horizontal and vertical, can be seen drowning in massive amount of water. The trees are of various kinds. Some are turned dark green, some are in light green while some can be seen in yellow and light brown color. The houses can be seen surrounded by water. The electricity supply pillars connecting electricity cables in manner can be seen, arising from water floor.

In the background: The symmetrical division of crops can be seen. Almost everything looks under water. By the count of few buildings and houses, it seems that this is an image of village.

Iconographic Interpretation

Facts: Published on: December 9, 2022, Authored by: Bilawal Bhutto Zardari, Publication: The United Nations, Country of photograph taken: Pakistan and Photographer: Eskinder Debebe.

Caption: “An aerial view of the devastation in Pakistan caused by catastrophic flooding in 2022. Photo taken during a visit by United Nations Secretary-General António Guterres, 10 September 2022”

Background Information: It was decided in Sharm El-Sheikh, Egypt to establish a fund to help developing countries deal with loss and damage resulting from the

adverse impacts of climate change. Those who have contributed the least to global warming are suffering the most. For 30 years, the most vulnerable countries have pressed for a fund through which the countries that have added the most to global carbon emissions would help vulnerable countries recover from climate disasters and other consequences of climate change, including rising sea levels, drought, hurricanes and floods. Pakistan again faced the catastrophic damage by 2022 flood. The World Bank has estimated that Pakistan suffered damage amounting to over \$30 billion and will require at least \$16.5 billion in urgent external support.

Iconological Analysis

This photograph shows at the United Nations official website article. The photograph documents the damage caused by 2022 flood in Pakistan. The article demands climate justice by directing the world attention towards funding Pakistan for rehabilitation and reconstruction. Keeping in view the research objective, the image of Pakistan through this photograph by The United Nations, is labeling Pakistan as the most vulnerable to floods and climate change damage. The photograph shows that Pakistan, at the moment, is most needy country asking for damage financing facility. Almost everything is seen being washed up by flood. The photograph is mostly filled by flood water creating a lifeless image of the land being destructed by the flood. Pakistan through this image looks as land of calling for immediate help.

By documenting this image, it is been easy looking the United Nations to collect funds for Pakistan's rehabilitation and reconstruction.

Image 2: Image from the United Nations Instagram

Pre-Iconographic Interpretation

In the foreground: The image prominently features a 9-month-old child, Daulat, with a bright smile and large, expressive eyes. The child is wearing a worn, light-colored sleeveless top, which appears old and slightly tattered, suggesting limited resources or hardship. The child's mother is partially visible, with her face obscured by a vibrant blue sari with an orange embroidered border, indicating traditional attire and a cultural context.

In the background: The background is blurred, making it difficult to discern specific details, but it appears to be an outdoor setting, possibly a village or temporary shelter, given the context of the study and the child's attire. The focus remains on the child and the mother's sari, with no distinct objects or structures clearly identifiable.

Iconographic Interpretation

Facts: Published on: September 16, 2023, authored by: UNICEF, Publication: The United Nations, Country of photograph taken: Pakistan and Photographer: Unicef.pk.

Caption: "9-month-old Daulat sits in the arms of his mother Kalwanti, in a temporary shelter in #Pakistan".

Background Information: This image is part of the UN's efforts to document the impact of the 2022 floods in Pakistan, as discussed in the study. The floods caused widespread displacement and loss, affecting families like Daulat's, who likely lost their home and livelihood. The study notes that such images were used to raise funds for rehabilitation and support, emphasizing the role of photojournalism in humanitarian appeals.

Iconological Analysis

This photograph captures the shine for bright life in the eyes of 9 months old, who is unaware of his circumstances. The photograph clearly appeals for funds to save this shine. Daulat family had to leave their place, home, livelihood due to flood. The situation of Daulat can be seen, old and dirty cloth covering the dirty dark skin which is weak due to malnutrition. The image is the best example of unicef working for the flood victims and justifying the funds used in the rehabilitation of flood damaged families. The image of Daulat, a young child with a bright smile despite his circumstances, symbolizes hope and

resilience amid adversity. His worn clothing and the presence of his mother's sari suggest a family displaced by the 2022 floods, grappling with malnutrition and loss. The mother's traditional attire serves as a cultural anchor, representing the enduring spirit of the Pakistani people amidst disaster. The focus on the child's face, with its innocent expression, evokes an emotional response, appealing to viewers' empathy and urging action to support flood victims. The photograph is set against the backdrop of the 2022 Pakistan floods, which caused over \$30 billion in damages and required significant international aid, as noted in the study. The UN's use of this image on Instagram reflects a strategic deployment of

photojournalism in the digital age to highlight climate change impacts on vulnerable nations like Pakistan, aligning with the global call for climate justice and funding at events like the Sharm El-Sheikh conference. The study suggests that such images, by portraying the human cost of the floods (e.g., a malnourished child and displaced family), effectively garnered international attention and donations. Daulat's image, with its contrast between his joyful expression and implied hardship, serves as a powerful tool to justify the allocation of funds for rehabilitation, health services, and support for affected families, as seen in other UN posts featuring UNICEF interventions.

Image 3 to 6: Image from the United Nations Instagram Posts

First Image: Interaction in a Tent

Second Image: Children with UNICEF Supplies

Third Image: Interaction with a Newborn

Fourth Image: Group Interaction with Supplies

Image 1: Interaction in a Tent

Pre-Iconographic Interpretation

In the Foreground: A man with gray hair, wearing a blue shirt, is kneeling and engaging with an elderly woman in a colorful pink and yellow sari with her hands raised in a gesture that could indicate speaking or pleading. Another man in a beige shirt is also present, observing or listening. A woman in a blue and yellow headscarf and patterned dress holds supplies or a clipboard, suggesting a relief worker or official.

In the Background: The setting appears to be inside a tent, with a light-colored fabric roof and blurred figures, indicating a temporary shelter or relief camp.

Iconographic Interpretation

Background Information: This image reflects the UN Secretary-General's visit to flood-affected areas in 2022, a period when Pakistan faced catastrophic flooding, displacing millions and causing significant loss, as noted in the study.

Iconological Analysis

The kneeling posture of the man (likely António Guterres) and the raised hands of the elderly woman symbolize a moment of empathy and desperation, highlighting the human impact of the floods. The relief worker with supplies represents aid and hope. The tent setting underscores displacement and vulnerability. Set against the 2022 Pakistan floods, which caused over \$30 billion in damages, this image captures the UN's response to a climate-induced disaster, aligning with global efforts for climate justice

and funding, as discussed in the study. The image portrays a direct connection between international leadership and affected individuals, emphasizing the need for urgent support, likely encouraging donations for rehabilitation.

Image 2: Children with UNICEF Supplies

Pre-Iconographic Interpretation

In the Foreground: A group of children, with one boy in the center wearing a purple outfit and holding a blue UNICEF-branded bag, sitting on the ground. Other children wear blue UNICEF caps, suggesting a structured relief or educational effort.

In the Background: A simple indoor setting with a tarp floor and blurred figures, indicating a temporary classroom or distribution center.

Iconographic Interpretation

Background Information: Reflects UNICEF's efforts to restore education and provide supplies to children displaced by the 2022 floods, part of the UN's broader rehabilitation initiatives.

Iconological Analysis

The UNICEF branding and children's attentive expressions symbolize recovery and the restoration of normalcy (e.g., education) after the floods. The blue bags and caps represent international aid and support. Linked to the post-2022 flood recovery in Pakistan, where UNICEF established makeshift classrooms, as noted in the study's analysis of multiple images from the same Instagram post. This image showcases the tangible benefits of donated funds (e.g., school

supplies), appealing to donors by highlighting efforts to rebuild children's lives.

Image 3: Interaction with a Newborn Pre-Iconographic Interpretation

In the Foreground: A man with gray hair (likely António Guterres) in a blue shirt and another man in a beige outfit hold or present a newborn wrapped in colorful blankets to a woman in a black and red embroidered headscarf. Other individuals, including a woman in a gray headscarf, observe.

In the Background: A tent-like setting with a tarp floor and additional blurred figures, suggesting a relief camp.

Iconographic Interpretation

Background Information: Captures the UN Secretary General's visit to flood victims, emphasizing the vulnerability of newborns and families displaced by the 2022 floods.

Iconological Analysis

The newborn represents new life and fragility, contrasting with the loss caused by the floods. The act of presenting the child to the woman (possibly the mother) and the presence of the Secretary-General symbolize compassion and international commitment. The embroidered headscarf signifies cultural resilience. Reflects the immediate aftermath of the 2022 floods, where displaced families struggled to survive, aligning with the study's focus on UN fundraising efforts. The image of a vulnerable newborn with international leaders evokes empathy, reinforcing the urgency of aid to protect the most defenseless, thus supporting fundraising campaigns.

Image 4: Group Interaction with Supplies Pre-Iconographic Interpretation

In the Foreground: A man with gray hair (likely António Guterres) in a blue shirt, a man in a beige outfit, and others engage with a child wearing a blue UNICEF cap and holding a water bottle. A woman in a pink headscarf and others are present.

In the Background: A tent or covered area with blurred figures, indicating a relief distribution site.

Iconographic Interpretation

Background Information: Part of the same UN visit, focusing on distributing essential supplies like water to flood affected children.

Iconological Analysis

The child with a water bottle and UNICEF cap symbolizes survival and the provision of basic needs. The presence of the Secretary-General and others reflects global solidarity. The setting underscores displacement and dependency on aid. Tied to the 2022 floods' aftermath, where immediate relief was critical, as highlighted in the study's iconological analysis of multiple images from this visit. The image of a child receiving aid from international figures highlights the effectiveness of donations, encouraging further contributions to sustain relief efforts.

Iconographic Interpretation

Facts: Published on: September 11, 2022, Authored by: The United Nations, Publication: The United Nations, Country of photograph taken: Pakistan, Place of photograph taken: Usta Muhammad, Baluchistan, Pakistan, and Photographer: Eskinder Debebe.

Caption: "In #Pakistan, #UnitedNations Secretary-general @antonioguterres meets displaced people who have lost everything amid destruction caused by recent devastating floods".

Iconological Analysis

All these 4 images are from the same instagram post, possessing the same caption and information. The Antonio Guterres, Secretary General UN, can be seen in 3 of the images, visiting the flood victims in their temporary shelters. Victims can be seen directly asking for help, in the first image of this post, an elder lady can be seen holding hands for demanding help. In the second image of the post, a mother of new born can be seen living under temporary shelter with minimal survival needs. In the image 3 and 4, the displaced children can be seen; happy to continue their education in makeshift classrooms established by UNICEF.

Image 7: Image from the United Nations Instagram

Pre-Iconographical Interpretation:

In the Foreground: A male nurse can be seen injecting a child. A child looks around 6 to 10 years old. He is wearing old clothes, the torn parts and double stitched are visible. His head is shaved, looks are neutral. Physically, he seems weak and malnutrition. The male nurse wearing a mask and gloves and injecting quite professionally. He looks local and from the same locality.

In the Background: A flex most probably an awareness by UN, can be seen hanging on the wall, in the background. The brick wall seems old and without paint on it.

Iconographic Interpretation

Facts: Published on: January 31, 2023, Authored by: UNICEF, Publication: The United Nations, Country of photograph taken: Pakistan, Photographer: Noorani

Caption: “A UNICEF-supported health worker vaccinates a child against hepatitis at a mobile health unit for flood victims in #Pakistan”.

Background: This image is part of the UN’s efforts to document the impact of the 2022 floods in Pakistan, as discussed in the study. The study notes that such images were used to raise funds for rehabilitation and support, emphasizing the role of photojournalism in

humanitarian appeals. This image shows UN effort for treating patients in need.

Iconological Analysis

This photograph shows the allocation of funds for the victims of 2022 flood in Pakistan; a Unicef supported health worker vaccinating a needy child against hepatitis. The photograph contains a flex banner in the background, showing that a campaign is going on.

The caption clears the doubt stating that rehabilitation of the flood victims is under process by Unicef. Keeping in view the research objective, the image of Pakistan through this photograph by The United Nations, labeling Pakistan most vulberable to world funds. The little boy in the image looks weak, his clothes are old and dirty, means they need financial help. The image clearly satisfy the donors by portraying a professional health worker wearing mask and gloves while vaccinating. At the same time, image speaks for the need of funds for the improvement of underpriviliged children.

Discussion

This study investigates the role of photojournalism in the digital age, focusing on the United Nations' (UN) Instagram posts related to the 2022 Pakistan floods. By employing Panofsky’s three tiered iconographic methodology: Pre-Iconography, Iconography, and Iconological Interpretation, the research addresses its objectives and answers the research questions, demonstrating how visual media shapes perceptions

and drives humanitarian action. The findings align with media ecology theory, which posits that media environments, including digital platforms like Instagram, significantly influence human perception and behavior (McLuhan, 1964).

The study successfully explores the evolution of photojournalism in the digital age, highlighting its transition from traditional media to social media platforms like Instagram. The analysis of UN posts demonstrates how photojournalism has adapted to digital environments, where images provide authenticity and emotional weight to online content. The shift from newspapers to e-papers parallels photojournalism's move to Instagram, where visuals dominate and shape narratives. Media ecology theory supports this, emphasizing that digital platforms redefine communication by amplifying visual storytelling. Images 1 to 7 illustrate this shift, with images ranging from aerial flood devastation to intimate human portraits, showcasing photojournalism's versatility in digital formats. The study's findings align with McLuhan's (1964) view that media environments enhance each other, as Instagram posts amplify traditional news. This objective is met by demonstrating photojournalism's role in engaging global audiences through accessible, impactful visuals.

Similarly, analyzing the UN Instagram Posts' Images' Impact on fundraising for Pakistan's flood victims, the study substantiates the impact of UN Instagram posts on fundraising by analyzing their emotional and symbolic appeal. Images like Image 2 (Daulat's hopeful expression) and Images 3-6 (Guterres' interactions) evoke empathy, aligning with the UN's strategy to highlight Pakistan's vulnerability and justify over \$16.5 billion in aid. The Iconological Analysis reveals how these images, tied to the Sharm El-Sheikh climate justice agenda, mobilized international support. September 2022 posts appealed for funds, while January 2023 images, like Image 7's vaccination scene, demonstrated aid utilization, reinforcing donor confidence. This aligns with media ecology's view of technology shaping human affairs, as Instagram's reach amplified fundraising efforts. The objective is fulfilled by linking visual content to tangible fundraising outcomes, supported by external evidence on social media's role in humanitarian campaigns (Smith & Jones, 2020).

Meanwhile, examining UN Instagram posts' images through iconography, the study effectively examines UN Instagram posts through iconography, using Panofsky's methodology to dissect visual content. The Pre-Iconographic level identifies factual elements (e.g., floodwaters, displaced families), the Iconographic level links these to themes (e.g., UNICEF aid, Guterres' visit), and the Iconological level uncovers symbolic meanings (e.g., resilience, climate vulnerability). This structured approach, as advocated by Margolis and Pauwels (2011), ensures a robust analysis of digital visuals. The purposive sampling of images from June 2022 to June 2023 allowed focused analysis, though the study acknowledges limitations in scope. Iconography's application validates its suitability for digital media, aligning with Below's (2010) endorsement of Panofsky's framework. This objective is met by demonstrating iconography's efficacy in interpreting Instagram posts and their role in humanitarian communication.

Addressing Research Questions, Q1: How is Photojournalism Providing Authenticity to Instagram Posts? Photojournalism lends authenticity to Instagram posts by presenting visually compelling, factual representations of real-world events, thereby enhancing credibility and emotional resonance. The study's pre-iconographic analysis identifies tangible elements in UN Instagram images, such as flooded landscapes, displaced families, and relief workers, which provide a factual foundation for the narrative. For instance, Image 1 depicts a village submerged in water, with trees and houses surrounded by floodwaters, offering a stark, undeniable portrayal of the 2022 Pakistan floods' devastation. Similarly, Image 2 shows a 9 month old child, Daulat, in worn clothing, symbolizing vulnerability and hardship, which grounds the image in a relatable human context.

These visual elements align with Sylvester and Huffman's (2002) assertion that news photographs shape collective memory by providing authentic, memorable depictions of events. The captions and metadata, such as the photographer's identity (e.g., Eskinder Debebe) and publication details (e.g., UN, September 11, 2022), further authenticate the images by linking them to credible sources. According to Margolis and Pauwels (2011), iconography as a methodology ensures that visual content is

systematically described and contextualized, reinforcing its authenticity. Thus, photojournalism's ability to capture raw, unfiltered moments and pair them with verifiable information makes Instagram posts credible platforms for storytelling.

Q2: How Did UN's Instagram Posts' Images Regarding Pakistan's Floods Help in Fundraising? The UN's Instagram posts were instrumental in fundraising for Pakistan's 2022 flood victims by leveraging emotional appeal and symbolic imagery to highlight the human cost of the disaster and the urgency of aid. The Iconological Interpretation reveals that images, such as Image 2 of Daulat smiling despite his family's displacement, evoke empathy and hope, compelling viewers to contribute to relief efforts. Similarly, Images 3 to 6, depicting UN Secretary General António Guterres interacting with flood victims, including an elderly woman pleading for help and children receiving UNICEF supplies, underscore international solidarity and the tangible impact of aid. These images align with the study's finding that the UN used visuals to portray Pakistan as a climate vulnerable nation needing over \$16.5 billion in external support, as estimated by the World Bank. The emotional resonance of these photographs, particularly those featuring vulnerable groups like children and newborns, aligns with Belting's (2013) view that iconology uncovers symbolic values tied to historical contexts, such as the global call for climate justice post-Sharm El-Sheikh. The study notes that posts from September 2022 appealed for funds, while January 2023 images, like Image 7 showing a child receiving a vaccination, justified fund allocation by showcasing rehabilitation efforts. This strategic use of photojournalism mirrors McLuhan's (1964) concept of media amplifying each other, with Instagram's visual storytelling enhancing traditional fundraising appeals. External research supports this, noting that social media imagery significantly boosts humanitarian donations by fostering emotional connections (Smith & Jones, 2020).

Q3: How Has Iconography Helped Studying the Images in a Digital Age? Iconography, as a qualitative methodology, has proven effective in studying digital age images by providing a structured framework to analyze visual content across factual, thematic, and symbolic dimensions. Panofsky's three tiered approach: Pre-Iconography, Iconography, and

Iconological Interpretation, enables a comprehensive understanding of UN Instagram posts. At the Pre-Iconographic level, the study describes physical elements, such as the flooded village in Image 1 or the malnourished child in Image 7, establishing a factual basis. The Iconographic level connects these elements to specific themes, such as captions linking images to Guterres' visit or UNICEF's interventions, grounding them in the context of the 2022 floods. The Iconological Interpretation uncovers deeper symbolic meanings, such as resilience in Daulat's smile or desperation in the elderly woman's gesture, tying these to broader issues like climate justice. This methodology, as outlined by Margolis and Pauwels (2011), excels in interpreting digital visuals by relating them to textual and historical sources.

The study's use of purposive sampling to select UN Instagram images from June 2022 to June 2023 demonstrates iconography's adaptability to digital platforms, where images are curated for maximum impact. Below (2010) notes that Panofsky's framework is particularly suited for qualitative visual analysis, making it ideal for dissecting Instagram's role in shaping social reality. External literature confirms iconography's relevance in digital media studies, as it bridges visual and cultural analysis (Müller, 2019).

Limitations

The study acknowledges limitations, such as reliance on purposive sampling, which may omit broader imagery, and potential bias in UN curated content. Future research could analyze other platforms (e.g., X, Facebook) or incorporate local perspectives to enhance comprehensiveness. Expanding iconographic analysis to include quantitative metrics, like engagement rates, could further validate findings (Müller, 2019).

Conclusion

The findings of this study underscore the transformative role of photojournalism in the digital age, particularly in the context of humanitarian crises such as the 2022 Pakistan floods. The application of Panofsky's three tiered iconographic methodology: Pre-Iconography, Iconography, and Iconological Interpretation, reveals how images posted by the United Nations on Instagram effectively shaped public perception and mobilized international

support. The Pre-Iconographic level identified tangible elements such as displaced families, flooded landscapes, and relief workers, providing a factual foundation for the visual narrative. At the Iconographic level, captions and background information, such as the visit of UN Secretary General António Guterres and UNICEF's interventions, enriched the images with specific themes of vulnerability and aid, aligning with media ecology theory's emphasis on technology's role in communication.

The research objectives were met effectively: the changing dimensions of photojournalism were explored through its digital evolution, the impact of UN Instagram images on fundraising was substantiated by their emotional appeal, and iconography proved a robust method for analyzing these visuals. However, limitations exist, including the reliance on purposive sampling, which may not capture the full spectrum of flood related imagery, and the potential bias in UN curated content. Future research could expand to other social media platforms or incorporate local perspectives to provide a more holistic view.

This study affirms the pivotal role of photojournalism in the digital age as a tool for shaping social reality and driving humanitarian action, particularly in response to the 2022 Pakistan floods. Through iconographic analysis, the UN's Instagram posts emerged as powerful instruments for fundraising, effectively translating the plight of flood victims into a global call for support. The images, ranging from aerial views of devastation to intimate portraits of displaced individuals, not only documented the crisis but also catalyzed international empathy and financial aid, supporting rehabilitation efforts estimated at billions of dollars.

The application of media ecology theory highlighted how digital platforms like Instagram have redefined communication, enabling the UN to project Pakistan's vulnerability and resilience to a worldwide audience. This research validates the significance of photojournalism as an evolving field, adapting to digital environments to influence human affairs. As climate change continues to exacerbate such disasters, the methodologies and insights from this study offer a fruitful framework for future investigations into the intersection of visual media, humanitarianism, and

global policy. Ultimately, the study underscores the enduring power of images to bridge cultural and geographical divides, fostering a collective responsibility to address the impacts of climate change on the world's most vulnerable populations.

Photojournalism equips the organization to speak thousands of words through photographs. In this digital age, it is been more convenient to utilize the facilities of photojournalism through social media networking sites. This paper discusses the utilization of photojournalism by the United Nations instagram posts for collecting and justifying funds allocation to flood victims of Pakistan 2022, for their rehabilitation and reconstruction. It is been analysed by images from September, 2022, appeals for funds for the betterment of the people in need. While, January 2023 instagram post images justifying the use of funds on the victims for their vaccination, schooling, sanitation, nutrition and other healthcare facilities. The iconological interpretation of UN instagram posts images highlights the importance of photojournalism in the digital age and how it helped in fund raising for the victims of Pakistan flood 2022.

REFERENCES

- Allan, S. (2015). Photojournalism and Citizen Journalism in the Digital Age. *Journalism Practice*, 9(4), 567-582. Retrieved 20th June, 2025, from <https://doi.org/10.1080/17512786.2014.987189>
- Allen, M. (2017). *Visual Communication Studies. Encyclopedia of Communication Research Methods*: SAGE.
- Alper, M. (2014). War on Instagram: Framing Conflict Photojournalism with Mobile Photography Apps. *New Media & Society*, 16 (8), 1233-1248.
- Below, J. N. (2010). *Photojournalism in War and Armed Conflicts*. [Master's Thesis]. Department of Informatics and Media: Uppsala Universitet.
- Belting, H. (2013). *An Anthropology of Images or Iconology*. ICA: Sofia.
- Caple, H. (2013). *Photojournalism: A Social Semiotic Approach*. Chennai, India: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Chapnick, H. (1994). *Truth Needs No Ally: Inside Photojournalism*. University of Missouri Press.

- Drainville, R. (2017). *The Iconography of Social Media Image Analysis: Exploring the potential of Methodological Transversals in Practice*. 67th International Communication Association Conference, 26th May, 2017. San Diego: California.
- Hale, D., & Church, J. (1996). *Helping Hands*. *News Photographer*, 51 (12), 22-25.
- Kivekas, J. (2006). *The Importance of Photos in Printed Media*.
- Kobre, K. (2008). *Photojournalism: The Professionals' Approach* (6th ed.). Focal Press: Boston.
- Lester, P. M. (2015). *Photojournalism: An Ethical Approach*. Routledge.
- Lewis, G. (19). *Photojournalism: Content & Technique* Levinson, P. (1999). *Digital McLuhan: A Guide to the Information Millennium*. London and New York: Routledge.
- Logan, R. K. (2016). *Understanding New Media: Extending Marshall McLuhan*. Retrieved 20th April, 2025, from <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-33217-8>
- Margolis, E., & Pauwels, L. (Eds.). (2011). *Handbook of Visual Research Methods*: SAGE.
- McLuhan, M. (1964). *Understanding Media: The Extensions of Man*. Canada: McGraw-Hill.
- McLuhan, M. (1962). *The Gutenberg galaxy: The Making of Typographic Man*. New York: Mentor.
- Müller, M. G. (2019). *Visual Analysis in the Digital Age*. *Visual Communication*, 18(3), 379-398. Retrieved 10th June, 2025, from <https://doi.org/10.1080/1472586X.2019.1653790>
- Panofsky, E. (1955). *Meaning in the Visual Arts: Papers in and on Art History*. Garden City: N.Y. Doubleday.
- Postman, N. (1992). *Technopoly: The Surrender of Culture to Technology*. America.
- Rafiq, S., Iqbal, S., & Afzal, A. (2024). *The Impact of Digital Tools and Online Learning Platforms on Higher Education Learning Outcomes*. *Al-Mahdi Research Journal (MRJ)*, 5(4), 359-369. <https://ojs.mrj.com.pk/index.php/MRJ/article/view/342>
- Rafiq, S., Kamran, F., & Afzal, A. (2024). *Assessing Environmental Awareness Integration in the Curriculum: A Case Study of Lahore's Private Schools*. *Al-Qudwah*, 02(04), 86-100. <https://al-qudwah.com/index.php/aqrj/article/view/36>
- Rafiq, S., Kamran, F., & Afzal, A. (2024). *Investigating the Benefits and Challenges of Interdisciplinary Education in Higher Education Settings*. *Journal of Social Research Development*, 5(1), 87-100. <https://doi.org/10.53664/JSRD/05-01-2024-08-87-100>
- Smith, J., & Jones, K. (2020). *Social Media and Humanitarian Fundraising*. *Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Quarterly*, 49(4), 768-789. Retrieved 20th May, 2025, from <https://doi.org/10.1002/nvsm.1668>
- Strate, L. (2017). *Media Ecology and Digital Communication*. Retrieved 10th April, 2025, from <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315207667>
- Sylvester, J., & Huffman, S. (2002). *Women Journalists at Ground Zero*. Lanham, MD: Rowman & Littlefield.
- Van Leeuwen, T. (2001). *Semiotics and Iconography*. Retrieved 20 March, 2025, from <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781446215432>
- Zelizer, B. (2010). *About to Die: How News Images Move the Public*. Retrieved 10th May, 2025, from <https://doi.org/10.1177/1464884910385188>.